

A study on the use of intraperitoneal normal saline to reduce shoulder pain post-laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 22(03), 561-565

Publication history: Received on 19 May 2025; revised on 25 June 2025; accepted on 28 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.22.3.0643>

Abstract

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is widely regarded as the treatment of choice for symptomatic cholelithiasis, offering several benefits over open surgery, such as reduced postoperative discomfort. Despite this, shoulder tip pain remains a common postoperative issue, impacting both recovery and patient satisfaction. This study seeks to assess the effectiveness of different analgesic interventions in reducing shoulder tip pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Through the evaluation of patient outcomes and pain control methods, the goal is to determine the most effective strategies to support recovery and enhance patient comfort and satisfaction.

Material and Methods: This prospective comparative study involved 80 patients scheduled for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy, who were randomly assigned into two groups: a control group (no irrigation) and an intervention group receiving intraperitoneal instillation of 1000 ml of normal saline warmed to 37°C. Postoperative pain was evaluated using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 6, 18, and 24 hours. Additionally, the requirement for analgesics within the first 24 hours was documented for both groups.

Results: The normal saline group showed a significant reduction in shoulder tip pain at 6 hours ($P=0.031$) and 18 hours ($P=0.029$) postoperatively compared to the control group, with no notable difference at 24 hours ($P=0.152$). Mean pain intensity was also significantly lower at 6 hours ($P=0.002$) and 18 hours ($P=0.037$). Analgesic requirements were significantly less in the saline group during the first 6 hours ($P=0.014$), with no significant difference observed afterward.

Conclusion: Intraperitoneal instillation of normal saline significantly alleviates early postoperative shoulder pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This technique is simple, safe, and may be effectively integrated into routine surgical protocols to improve patient recovery and comfort.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy; Shoulder Tip Pain; Intraperitoneal Saline; Postoperative Pain

1. Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is widely regarded as the treatment of choice for symptomatic cholelithiasis and cholecystitis, offering numerous advantages over conventional open surgery. These benefits include smaller surgical incisions, reduced blood loss, shorter durations of postoperative ileus, decreased hospital stays, faster overall recovery, and an earlier return to normal daily activities and work routines [1]. A key advantage of this minimally invasive approach is the reduction in postoperative pain compared to open procedures. Nevertheless, postoperative pain remains a significant issue, with patients commonly experiencing back pain, port site discomfort, and referred shoulder

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tip pain [2]. Shoulder pain, in particular, is notably frequent, affecting approximately 12% to 60% of patients, with peak intensity typically occurring within the first few hours' post-surgery and resolving within 2–3 days [3].

The causes of postoperative pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy are diverse. A major contributing factor is phrenic nerve irritation due to carbon dioxide insufflation during surgery, which leads to peritoneal irritation and an acidic intra-abdominal environment [3]. Additionally, individual differences and sociocultural influences may also play a role in pain perception. Despite advancements in surgical methods, managing postoperative pain effectively remains a clinical challenge. Several pain relief strategies have been explored, including NSAIDs, opioids, gas evacuation, and intraperitoneal instillation of normal saline or local anesthetics. Although the intraperitoneal administration (IPI) of saline and anesthetics has shown potential in pain reduction, inconsistent results and possible adverse effects necessitate further investigation [4]. This study, therefore, aims to evaluate the effectiveness of intraperitoneal saline instillation in minimizing shoulder pain after laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

2. Methodology

This prospective comparative study was carried out in the Department of General Surgery at Sree Mookambika Institute of Medical Science to evaluate the effectiveness of normal saline irrigation in reducing postoperative pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Adult patients aged between 18 and 75 years scheduled for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy were included after obtaining informed consent.

Patients with a history of opioid, steroid, NSAID, or alcohol use were excluded, along with those diagnosed with acute cholecystitis, gangrenous or empyematous gallbladder. Other exclusion criteria included conversion to open surgery, gallbladder rupture, bile leakage, or bleeding at the surgical site that could lead to peritoneal irritation. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups: the control group (no irrigation) and the intervention group, which received 1000 mL of 0.9% normal saline at 37°C infused over the surgical field, liver surface, and beneath the right hemidiaphragm.

All procedures were performed by a single experienced surgeon using a standardized 4-trocar laparoscopic technique. Pneumoperitoneum was established with CO₂ insufflation via a periumbilical trocar, maintaining an intra-abdominal pressure of 14 mm Hg. A nasogastric tube was placed post-intubation and removed at the conclusion of surgery.

Postoperative pain was measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 6, 18, and 24 hours, as well as one week after surgery. Additional information collected included patient demographics (age, gender, medical history, smoking status) and the frequency of analgesic requests within the first 24 hours postoperatively. This structured approach ensured consistency in assessing the role of normal saline irrigation in managing postoperative pain.

3. Results

In [Table 1], total of 80 patients was enrolled in the study, with 40 participants in each group (control and normal saline groups). The mean age of participants was comparable between the two groups (44.61±11.15 years in the control group vs. 42.36±12.19 years in the normal saline group). The distribution of gender was similar, with 14 males and 26 females in the control group compared to 12 males and 28 females in the normal saline group. The prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) was slightly higher in the control group (9 vs. 7), whereas hypertension (HTN) was more frequent in the normal saline group (11 vs. 8). The mean duration of pneumoperitoneum was significantly longer in the normal saline group (55.29±13.58 minutes) compared to the control group (45.75±9.47 minutes).

Table 1 Demographic distribution of study participants

Characteristics	Control group (n=40)	Normal saline group (n=40)
Age	44.61±11.15	42.36±12.19
Gender (M/F)	14/26	12/28
DM	9	7
HTN	8	11
Time of pneumoperitoneum (mins)	45.75±9.47	55.29±13.58

Table 2 Comparison of Shoulder Tip Pain among Study Participants

Group		Control group	Normal saline group	P value
Left shoulder tip pain	At 6 hours	3.1±1.9	1.8±2.6	0.031
	At 18 hours	2.8±1.9	1.7±1.9	0.029
	At 24 hours	2.1±1.6	1.4±2.1	0.152
Right shoulder tip pain	At 6 hours	3±2.1	1.9±1.9	0.038
	At 18 hours	2.4±1.8	1.5±1.8	0.016
	At 24 hours	1.9±1.6	1.3±1.8	0.178
Mean pain intensity of shoulders	At 6 hours	3.2±2.1	1.4±2.3	0.002
	At 18 hours	2.4±1.6	1.3±2.1	0.037
	At 24 hours	1.9±1.5	1.7±2.0	0.663

In [Table 2], the intensity of left shoulder tip pain was significantly lower in the normal saline group at 6 hours (1.8±2.6 vs. 3.1±1.9, P=0.031) and 18 hours postoperatively (1.7±1.9 vs. 2.8±1.9, P=0.029). However, at 24 hours, there was no significant difference between the groups (1.4±2.1 vs. 2.1±1.6, P=0.152). Similarly, right shoulder tip pain was significantly reduced in the normal saline group at 6 hours (1.9±1.9 vs. 3±2.1, P=0.038) and 18 hours (1.5±1.8 vs. 2.4±1.8, P=0.016), but no significant difference was observed at 24 hours (1.3±1.8 vs. 1.9±1.6, P=0.178).

When the mean pain intensity of both shoulders was considered, the normal saline group experienced significantly lower pain at 6 hours (1.4±2.3 vs. 3.2±2.1, P=0.002) and 18 hours (1.3±2.1 vs. 2.4±1.6, P=0.037). By 24 hours, the mean pain intensity difference between the groups was not statistically significant (1.7±2.0 vs. 1.9±1.5, P=0.663).

Table 3 Analgesia Demand among Study Participants

Number of analgesia demand over the 24 hours postoperatively	Control group	Normal saline group	P value
During the first 6 hour	1.65±0.48	1.375±0.49	0.014
Between 6 and 18 hours	0.9±0.71	1.1±0.84	0.254
Between 18 and 24 hours	0.525±0.51	0.475±0.51	0.66

In [Table 3], the normal saline group demonstrated a significantly lower number of analgesia demands during the first 6 hours postoperatively (1.375±0.49 vs. 1.65±0.48, P=0.014). Between 6 and 18 hours, the difference in analgesia demand was not statistically significant (1.1±0.84 vs. 0.9±0.71, P=0.254). Similarly, no significant difference was observed between 18 and 24 hours (0.475±0.51 vs. 0.525±0.51, P=0.66).

4. Discussion

Postoperative pain continues to be a major concern after laparoscopic cholecystectomy, with up to 80% of patients requiring analgesic support [5]. The pain intensity is highest during the initial hours after surgery and gradually subsides over 48 to 72 hours [6]. Research suggests that this pain primarily results from peritoneal irritation rather than somatic sources such as skin or muscle layers. A key contributor is the acidic environment created by carbon dioxide (CO₂) insufflation during pneumoperitoneum, which leads to peritoneal acidosis and subsequent irritation of the phrenic nerve, commonly manifesting as shoulder tip pain [7–10]. Innovative methods, such as three-port laparoscopic techniques, have been explored [11], although the timing of surgery—early versus late cholecystectomy—appears to have minimal impact on pain characteristics [12].

In the present study, patients who received intraperitoneal normal saline demonstrated significantly reduced shoulder tip pain at 6- and 18-hours post-surgery compared to those in the control group [11,12]. These findings align with earlier research suggesting that saline irrigation effectively removes residual CO₂ from the subdiaphragmatic area, thereby lessening peritoneal irritation and referred pain [13,14]. The normal saline group also exhibited a lower mean shoulder

pain score during the same periods. However, by 24 hours, the difference in pain scores between the two groups was no longer statistically significant, indicating that the benefit of saline irrigation is most prominent in the early postoperative phase.

Analgesic demand during the first 6 hours was significantly lower in the saline group, although there was no notable difference in analgesic use between 6 and 24 hours postoperatively. This suggests that while intraperitoneal saline helps alleviate immediate postoperative discomfort, its influence on total analgesic use within the first 24 hours is limited [15].

These results support the use of intraperitoneal normal saline irrigation as a straightforward, safe, and cost-effective method to reduce early postoperative pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Nonetheless, further studies involving broader populations and extended follow-up are recommended to validate these findings and refine pain management protocols [16]. Although laparoscopy is frequently employed to evaluate unexplained abdominal pain, postoperative discomfort after laparoscopic procedures remains a clinical challenge [17].

5. Conclusion

Intraperitoneal irrigation with normal saline significantly reduces early postoperative shoulder pain, especially within the first 6 to 18 hours following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This method is simple, economical, and safe, effectively addressing pain caused by residual CO₂ and diaphragmatic irritation. While its impact on overall analgesic use is limited beyond the immediate postoperative phase, the early pain relief it offers makes it a valuable adjunct in improving postoperative recovery.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards. Approval was obtained from the appropriate ethics committee.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study

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